

**TRIBAL RELIGION AS A MEANS OF COMMUNICATION
BETWEEN NATURAL AND SUPERNATURAL ENTITIES: A CASE
STUDY FROM THE SANTAL TRIBE**

*** Nayan Ruhidas & **Dr. Sudip Bhui**

Abstract

In eastern India, the Santals form one of the largest Indigenous groups, with a sizeable presence in Purulia district, West Bengal. Their system of religion, knowledge, social organization, and perspectives are greatly interconnected and based on a particular form of relationship with nature. Based on secondary sources only, this document attempts to describe the Santals' religious beliefs, practices, and forms of decision-making, as well as their worldviews. Based on ancient anthropological literature and the most recent scholarly works focusing on Purulia, this research shows that for the Santals, religion is not a distinct domain of life, and is integrated with all forms of social practices, including agriculture, health care, and community management. The article further shows that despite social and economic changes, traditional beliefs and practices continue to shape Santal life. By focusing on Purulia, the study situates broader Santal culture within a specific regional and ecological context. This study highlights Santal religion as a lived system of communication between the natural, social, and supernatural domains rather than as a separate institutional practice.

Keywords: Santals; Indigenous Religion; Bonga; Indigenous Knowledge; Worldview; Purulia; Tribal Society

* *Research Scholar in Anth. & Tribal Studies, SKBU*

* *Associate Professor in Anth. & Tribal Studies, SKBU*

1. Introduction

Studying Pagan beliefs and the associated world-views is invaluable to understanding the perspectives of Indigenous peoples concerning existence, the cosmos, and social order. In the tribal communities of India, the Santals have been the focus of academics for long periods of time for their distinctive cultural practices, vibrant communal social organizations, and integration into their natural environments. Roy (1912) and Bodding (1925) have shown, in early cultural anthropology, that the religion of the Santals is not temple-centred, nor does it have a formal written doctrine; rather, it is a way of life that is social and economic.

Religion among the Santals gives a framework for understanding health and illness, and success and failure, and morals; it also aids in understanding the phenomena of nature. Santals do not segregate the sacred from the mundane, and their belief system explains the world as a continually active field with integrated and interdependent human beings, nature, and the supernatural. This integrated understanding of life forms the basis of the Santal worldview (Bose, 1941).

In West Bengal, the Santals are mainly concentrated in the western districts, particularly Purulia. Purulia district is marked by undulating land, forest cover, lateritic soil, and uncertain rainfall. These features of the environment play a great role in the Santal's way of life and culture. Recent studies conducted in Purulia show that environmental conditions continue to shape religious practices, indigenous knowledge systems, and community organization among the Santals (Biswas & Bain, 2022).

This article sets out to present a report of the Santal religion, indigenous knowledge, decision

making practices and world view with focus on Purulia district. We looked at the topics of religion, knowledge, and social organization separately which in fact are very much inter related in the case of the Santals.

2. Research Questions

1. How does Santal religion function as a system of communication between the natural, social, and supernatural worlds in the context of Purulia district?
2. In what ways are religious beliefs and indigenous knowledge integrated in shaping everyday practices such as agriculture, healthcare, and environmental management among the Santals?
3. How do religious values and spiritual beliefs influence collective decision-making and social organization in Santal villages?
4. How does the Santal worldview interpret life, suffering, moral responsibility, and continuity in the face of contemporary social and economic change?

3. Research Objectives

Objectives of this study are:

1. To examine Santal religion as an integrated system linking nature, society, and the spirit world among the Santals of Purulia.
2. To analyse the role of indigenous knowledge and religious belief in guiding everyday practices and community-based decision-making.
3. To interpret the Santal worldview and assess its continuity and adaptation under changing social and economic conditions.

4. Methodology

The present study is descriptive research which is based entirely on secondary data. This approach is a well-established in research which looks at Indigenous groups' belief systems and social life

as reported in existing ethnographic and scholarly literature (Roy, 1912; Bodding, 1925).

This study used a systematic review of literature which includes classical ethnographic works, texts, and peer reviewed journal articles related to the Santal community. Foundational studies provide in depth descriptions of Santal religion, social organization and world view form the descriptive base of this research (Roy, 1912; Bose, 1941). Also, we looked at more recent region-specific studies which look at Purulia district to do an analytically contemporary interpretation of present practices, changes, and continuities (Biswas & Bain, 2022; Chakraborty, 2025).

A thematic descriptive analysis was employed to organize and interpret the literature. This study looked at key themes which included religion, indigenous knowledge, decision making, and world view which are studied across many sources. This approach of thematic synthesis is common in qualitative and interpretive research to compare findings and generate analytical understanding from existing studies rather than producing new empirical data (Datta, 1984). This analytical approach is informed by that of anthropology and philosophy which present religion as a lived world view embedded in social and ecological contexts rather than as a formal institutional system (Bose, 1941). By using many scholars' works, this study presents interpretations which are rooted in present academic work.

5. Findings

5.1 The Santal Community in Purulia, West Bengal

The Santals are an Austroasiatic speaking Indigenous group which has settled in Jharkhand, West Bengal, Odisha, and Bihar. Historical

reports tell of their slow migration to the forests and hills which they took up for agriculture and to which they could stick to their community practices (Roy, 1912). In Purulia district Santal villages are found by the forests and near to cultivable land which is a reflection of their natural resource dependence.

A Santal village is a single entity in which community is the core. We see in these villages a great degree of cooperation, shared labor, and collective responsibility. Also, it is noted that in most cases a sacred space which they term the *Jaherthan*, a place which is looked at as the home of very important village spirits. This place is protected and in fact is treated with respect by the villagers and in it they perform rituals related to village welfare. From studies in Purulia it can be seen that the *Jaherthan* still plays a very important role in what is present in the religious life of the people and also in environmental protection (Biswas & Bain, 2022).

In Purulia livelihood is very much based on rain fed agriculture and the forest resources. As rain fall is very irregular the Santals have had to depend on traditional ecological knowledge for their agricultural and resource management practices. This very close tie with nature has in turn strengthened their religious beliefs related to land, forests, and spirits. Research reports that which put forth that religious practices play a role in how communities interpret environmental uncertainty and also in which they fortify collective responsibility (Gope et al., 2025). Although Santal villages in Purulia have had greater interaction with state institutions, markets, and non-tribal groups' they have managed to preserve strong cultural continuity. They still use collective decision making, festivals and rituals as a framework for social life and maintaining their community identity. While

in Purulia the Santals do have a common culture what is also true is that this community is not homogeneous. Age, education, economic standing, and experience of migration have brought about these differences. Relatively younger people, especially those with educational qualifications and influenced by the town, may have different attitude toward the customs and practices of the old people. Such internal diversity is crucial to avoid the portrayal of Santal society as homogeneous and to situate the society in cultural change and continuity in a more sophisticated manner.

5.2 Religious Beliefs and Practices

Santal religion is that which holds the world to be home to what they term *Bonga* which are spiritual beings. These spirits are thought to intervention in natural events, health, social harmony, and moral order. Also, the Santals do not see the spirit world as remote; rather they see spirits to be very much a part of everyday life (Roy, 1912).

Out of many Bongas which they worship, *Marang Buru* is looked at as the top spirit and is related to hills and also the protection of the community. Also, we see other spirits which care for villages, forests, households, and ancestors. What is put forth by these spirits is that for best individual and collective well-being one has to maintain balance with them (Bodding, 1925).

Religious practices are a part of agricultural and seasonal cycles. Festivals such as *Baha*, *Sohrai*, and *Erok* mark different stages of cultivation and seasonal change. In these festivals they do offerings, animal sacrifice, music, dance, and large feasts. It is reported that through such festivals social unity is strengthened and collective identity reinforced (Socio-Cultural Practices of Santal Tribal Community. Also, religion plays a key role in health and healing.

Disease is perceived to have an effect both physically and spiritually. Sickness is treated with a mix of healers' medicine, medicinal plants, and spirit appeasement rituals. Modern healthcare is not as accessible in rural areas so recent ethnographic studies in Purulia have documented the use of traditional medicine (Chakraborty, 2025).

Santal religion is flexible and adaptive. While external religious influences have entered Santal society, traditional beliefs continue to exist alongside new practices. In Purulia research reports that many Santal still practice native rituals related to the land and their ancestors at the same time as they adopt other religious labels (Biswas & Bain, 2022).

These shifts occur alongside Santals' ongoing religious practices. Different levels of participation in the practices can be observed among them. The younger generation may attend the rituals as passive observers, without emotional connection; or, as cultural activities, in which spirituality is neither held nor expressed. It is perhaps the most obvious indication that rather than just being inherited, the Santal religion is actively being negotiated. It shifts the focus to the active adaptation, alteration and transformation of Santal traditions that is ongoing in the present as part of living traditions.

5.3 Indigenous Knowledge System of the Santals

The indigenous knowledge base of the Santals is very much a part of their day-to-day interaction with the environment and their religious perspective. This knowledge has built up over generations through what they saw, experienced and did as a group. It is not put down in books but passed on through oral means in the doings of daily life, in rituals, stories, songs and in

community events. Academics for a long time have reported that Santal indigenous knowledge is practical, place based and very much a part of their culture and spiritual life (Roy, 1912; Bodding, 1925).

Indigenous knowledge is crucial for the livelihood and survival of the inhabitants of Purulia district with its unique natural surroundings of sparse and unpredictable rainfall, dry and arid soils, and patches of forests. Farming here is primarily dependent on rainfall and the Santal community needs to have a knowledge base consisting of traditional insights regarding the types of soil, the crops and their cycles, and the prevailing seasons. Research indicates the Santal community is able to accurately predict rainfall and correspondingly time agriculture through their observance of natural indicators, the behaviors of specific bird species, the wind, and the flowering of various plants (Murmu et al., 2018).

The Santal knowledge system also has an aspect related to forest-based knowledge. Santals view forests as food and medicine providers and sacred spaces. Due to the presence of holy spirits, many trees, groves, and hills are protected by them. As a culturally and ecologically significant area *Jaherthan*, or sacred grove, is where religious practices take place and where related natural resources are conserved. Studies of sacred groves in Purulia, are said to support the conservation of biodiversity and the use of resources in a sustainable manner (Biswas & Bain, 2022).

Traditional healthcare knowledge forms a significant part of Santal indigenous knowledge. Illness is a result of what is perceived to be physical cause and also spiritual imbalance. Thus, healing practices, we see to include the use of medicinal plants together with ritual activities which in turn restore balance between the people

and the spirits. In Purulia we see that a great many medicinal plants are still used to treat what may be described as common illnesses in parts of the community which have little access to modern health care facilities (Chakraborty, 2025).

Knowledge related to healthcare is not limited to specialists. Many in the community have basic knowledge of medicinal plants and home remedies which they pass down to family and share within the community. Also, songs, myths and rituals play a role in the transfer of this info in a cultural and symbolic way.

The Santals are currently facing difficulties despite the continued relevance of their indigenous knowledge. Within the Santals, formal education shifting the livelihood practices, new forest regulations, and climate change are all posing challenges to the traditional knowledge transmission systems. The oral tradition system is further endangered by the loss of elders, who are the traditional knowledge custodians. Despite that it is still very much relevant, the Santals' indigenous knowledge is put to great stress. Formal education, changes in livelihoods, forest rules, and climate instability have broken up the past methods of knowledge transfer. Also, it is the gradual loss of elders which are the keepers of that knowledge which puts at risk the sustainability of oral traditions. These stresses bring to fore important issues related to indigenous knowledge and the requirement of its recognition and protection within the parameters of large-scale development.

Santal indigenous knowledge is not a static entity. Presently it is seen that Santals do adopt modern agricultural tools, education, and health care practices into their routine while at the same time they do not give up on their traditional knowledge. In fact, modern practices are used in conjunction with indigenous knowledge. This

coexistence of systems is of a very adaptive and responsive character (Gope et al., 2025).

5.4 Decision-Making and Social Organization

Decision making in Santal is very much a collective affair which is very much rooted in the village based social structure. The village is the main unit of governance which runs on a set of shared norms, customs, and moral values. Traditional leadership plays key role in organizing rituals, resolving issues and in the maintenance of community harmony (Roy, 1912).

Village leadership is supported by social and religious authority rather than formal power. Decisions are usually taken through discussion and consensus, reflecting the community-oriented nature of Santal society. A religious belief system centres on the idea that leaders are guided by the spirits of the village and are believed to strengthen this system. A voluntary compliance is encouraged by this belief, which legitimizes the decision and sustains the system. (Datta, 1984).

In the area of conflict resolution which is a key element of the decision-making process in Santal, we see that issues related to marriage, land, or interpersonal relationships are brought to the village council. The goal here is not punishment but to restore social balance. Also, we see that rituals play a role in the resolution process which in addition to solving the issue at hand also works to restore the spiritual balance which in the long term reduces conflict and enforces a sense of collective responsibility. Early ethnographic studies report that these practices are very much a part of the social fabric which they in fact do reduce long term conflict and at the same time foster a sense of group responsibility. (Bodding, 1925).

Moral behaviour is guided by religious and social norms. Actions that disturb social harmony are believed to invite misfortune not only for individuals but for the entire community. This belief fosters self-control, community participation, and hierarchical respect. Studies from Purulia indicate that moral systems still shape behaviour, particularly in rural areas where formal social structures are robust (Biswas & Bain, 2022).

Decision-making is also evident during festivals and rituals. Community participation in all aspects of major events is mandatory, and all ritualistic and material offerings and events are planned in a communal fashion. Festivals allow for bonding and social integration. These get together also play key role in the pass down of culture and in the creation of a collective identity (Saren, 2025).

Gender roles in decision-making have traditionally been male-dominated, particularly in formal village councils. Women, however, engage in managing household rituals, keep cultural memory, and support sustenance of social ties. Women's participation in decision-making on health, education, and welfare (in Development and Educational intervention programs) appears to be growing (Chakraborty, 2025).

In Santal society, decision making is a manifestation of a particular worldview which sees the social order, the religious (spiritual) order and the ecosystem in a unified whole. In the Santal worldview, decision making is not concerned solely with the immediate product, but with the spiritual and social health of the community as a whole, as it relates to harmony and the sustenance of spirit in the community.

5.6 Santal Worldview and Philosophy of Life

The Santal world view is based on that which human life, nature, and the spirit world are in a live and interconnected relationship. There is no division between the sacred and the secular in life; instead, what we see in the day-to-day doings of the community such as farming, healing, festivals and social interaction are all a part of a greater moral and spiritual order. This world view in turn molds how Santals see happiness, suffering, responsibility, and balance in life (Roy, 1912; Bose, 1941).

Nature is at the core of the Santal world view. They view forests, hills, rivers, land, and animals not as economic resources but as living spaces that are home to spiritual forces. Respect for nature is thus at the same time a moral issue and a religious practice. Harm done to land or forests is reported to disrupt spiritual balance which in turn may cause illness, crop failure, or social conflict. In a study of Purulia it is brought out that such beliefs still play a role in how people think about forest use and land management which includes the sacred groves and ritual sites (Biswas & Bain, 2022).

It is put forth that human identity is of a collective not individual nature. Personal identity is very much a product of one's clan, kinship, and village membership. Success and failure are rare in individual terms; instead, it is in relation to what is going on within the community and the, which is at large, spiritual health. This collective focus also puts out that there is a great deal of cooperation, sharing of resources and mutual support which we see in agricultural work and festivals (Datta, 1984).

Ancestral figures are very much a part of the Santal world view. Death is looked at as a passage to a different form of presence which is not the end of existence but a change. It is held that ancestors do in fact play a role in the present lives

of the living and that they perform rituals to maintain that which is respectful in our relationships with them. These beliefs reinforce continuity between past and present and strengthen respect for tradition (Bodding, 1925).

Suffering and misfortune are looked at through a moral and spiritual lens. Illness, accident, or poor harvest are put forth as results of social imbalance which in turn is a result of broken rituals or social norms or unhappy spirits. Instead of a focus on blame the response is usually a collective ritual to restore balance. Recent studies in Purulia report that this worldview which is a great support to communities in times of uncertainty and environmental risk by way of put forth shared accounts of what is going on and also which bring out collective responses (Chakraborty, 2025).

Overall, in the case of the Santal worldview we see a preponderance for balance, moderation, and harmony. It puts forth a way of living which is founded on social cohesiveness, respect for nature and continuity with ancestors' traditions. Also, in the transformed social settings this underpinning philosophy which we see in this culture still plays a role in moral evaluation and day to day decision making.

5.7 Contemporary Changes and Continuities

Over the past few decades, due to schooling, public programs, and more contact with the surrounding people, the Santal community of Purulia has gone through remarkable socio-economic transformation. The Roads, educational institutions, and audio-visual media offered and continue to offer new ideas and opportunities. But new ideas do not necessarily mean a loss of old traditions. Education has sparked a better understanding of the available and inaccessible right a person is entitled to, the kind and quality of employment a person can and does hold, and a

person's awareness beneficiary structures. Younger people have more seasonal and permanent migration options for employment. Work in Purulia has shown that the changes do not entirely erode the social cohesion of the community, people's culture, and customs, but have shifted the forms of their sustenance (Biswas & Bain, 2022).

Some Santal groups have taken up different religious practices, also many practice many at once. Also, it is true that belief in Bongas, sacred groves, and in their ancestors', spirits is very much a part of them. Research also shows that in families which have converted to other religions, they still practice the old rituals which relate to agriculture, ancestors, and the better good of the village (Biswas & Bain, 2022).

Indigenous knowledge systems face challenges due to environmental degradation, forest restrictions, and climate uncertainty. At the same time, we also see that although challenged Traditional Ecological Knowledge is still very much in play in agriculture, health care, and environmental management. In some cases, like that of the *Jaherthan* sacred grove it can be seen that religious practice is also a support for environmental conservation (Gope et al., 2025).

Decision-making structures have also adapted. There are now official government administrative structures, yet customary people's councils still manage social regulation and conflicts. Community activities, ceremonial events, and communal celebrations still function as forums of discourse and collective action. Studies conducted in Purulia reflect the value of these structures in preserving social cohesion in times of change (Biswas & Bain, 2022).

Overall, contemporary change among the Santals should be understood as selective adaptation

rather than cultural loss. Traditional beliefs and practices continue to provide a framework through which new ideas and institutions are interpreted and integrated.

6. Conclusion

This article has presented a descriptive account of Santal's religion, indigenous knowledge system, decision-making practices, and worldview, with special reference to Purulia district. Drawing entirely on secondary sources, including classical ethnographies and recent regional studies, the paper has shown that these aspects of Santal life are deeply interconnected.

Santal religion is based on beliefs in spirits, sacred natural areas, and ancestral presence. Indigenous knowledge comes from living in a place for a long time and is strengthened by ceremonies and daily activities. Instead of formal power alone, decisions are made by a group based on moral and spiritual ideals. These ideas come together to make a philosophy that stresses unity between people, nature, and the spirit world.

In the face of social and economic changes studies in Purulia report that there is great continuity in cultural values and practices. What we see is that traditional beliefs are not dying out but are in fact coexisting with modern education, health care, and livelihoods. In an academic perspective, this study puts forth to larger conversations on Indigenous religion, environmental ethics, and collective governance. This paper looks at Santal religion as a lived experience which in turn presents the relevance of Indigenous philosophy in present day talks of sustainability and social cohesion. It is important to grasp this world view in terms of which to conduct respectful engagement with Indigenous communities and to use in the design of culturally

relevant development policies in tribal areas like Purulia.

Reference

Biswas, S., & Bain, W. K. (2022). Intersecting knowledge with landscape: Traditional wisdom and environmental sustainability — A case study of Santal community of Purulia district of West Bengal. *Antrocom: Online Journal of Anthropology*, 18(2), 591–603.

Bodding, P. O. (1925). *Studies in Santal medicine and connected folklore*. Asiatic Society.

Bose, N. K. (1941). *The Hindu method of tribal absorption*. Science and Culture.

Chakraborty, S. (2025). The interplay of cultural beliefs, the environment and the traditional healthcare system among the Santals of Purulia, India. *Antrocom: Online Journal of Anthropology*, 21(1), 291–304.

Datta, S. (1984). *The Santals: Their culture and social life*. Inter-India Publications.

Gope, L., Kuiry, S., Mahato, S., & Karunamay, P. (2025). Indigenous Knowledge for Environmental Sustainability: A Case Study on the Santhal Community Indigenous Knowledge for Environmental Sustainability: A Case Study on the Santhal Community. *Journal: Boston Research Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities Boston Research Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities*, 5(1).

Murmu, E., Vasistha, H. B., & Adhikari, B. S. (2018). Traditional ecological knowledge of Santhal tribe of West Bengal with special reference to weather forecast and biodiversity conservation. *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*, 17(1), 127–135.

Socio-cultural and traditional practices of Santal tribal community. (2025). *The Academic*.

Saren, B. (2025). Socio-cultural and Traditional Practices of Santal Tribal Community in West Bengal. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(6). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15861462>